

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Novel protein-rich materials from rapeseed meal with enhanced mechanical behavior

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Figure S1. TG curves of specimens RM, RM-R2, RM-D1, RM-D2 and RM-R2D2 14%

RM-R0

RM

RM-R2

RM-D1

RM-D2

RM-R2D2-14%

Figure S2. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (cross section, room temperature) RM-R0, RM, RM-R2, RM-D1, RM-D2, RM-R2D2 14% at 300µm or 500µm

RM-R0

RM

RM-R2

RM-D1

RM-D2

RM-R2D2-14%

Figure S3. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (longitudinal section, room temperature) RM-R0, RM, RM-R2, RM-D1, RM-D2, RM-R2D2 14% at 500µm

RM-R0

RM

RM-R2

RM-D1

RM-D2

RM-R2D2 14%

Figure S4. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (cross section, room temperature) RM-R0, RM, RM-R2, RM-D1, RM-D2, RM-R2D2 14% at 100µm

Figure S5. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (longitudinal section, room temperature) RM-R0, RM and RM-R2 at 100µm to 2µm

RM-D1

RM-D2

Figure S6. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (longitudinal section, room temperature) D1 and D2 at 100µm to 10µm

RM-R2D2 14%

Figure S7. SEM of the rapeseed meal-based materials (longitudinal section, room temperature) RM-R2D2 14% at 100um to 20um